

LAW, LOGIC AND STRUCTURATION IN LEGAL SYSTEMATICS

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Does the legal system have a structure and system or they are taken into it from the outside? Neither principles, nor rules are given in themselves, separated from each other in a way classified in terms of the law's taxonomic systemicity as bearing their own separate meaning. All this can be but the result of a constitutive act. It is not logic itself that labels anything as a structuring or systematising element identified as either principle or rule but we, who ponder the mode of how to construct a sequence of distinction, deduction and justification conclusive enough to convince those controlling the issue we propose in the procedural hierarchy. Therefore the structuring features in law are construed and construing, constructed and constructing at the same time, for they do not and cannot exist in and by themselves at all.

[ПРАВО, ЛОГИКА И ПРИРОДА ПРАВОВОЙ СИСТЕМАТИКИ] Имеет ли правовая система структуру и систему или они привносятся в нее извне? Ни принципы, ни правила не даны сами по себе, не отделены друг от друга таким образом, чтобы классифицироваться с точки зрения таксономической системности права как несущие свой отдельный смысл. Все это может быть лишь результатом конституирующего акта. Не сама логика маркирует что-либо как структурирующий или систематизирующий элемент, идентифицируемый как принцип или правило, а мы, размышляющие о том, как построить последовательность различий, дедукции и обоснования, достаточно убедительную, чтобы убедить тех, кто контролирует вопрос, который мы предлагаем в процедурной иерархии. Поэтому структурирующие признаки в праве одновременно истолковываются и истолковываются, конструируются и конструируются, ибо они не существуют и не могут существовать сами по себе.

1. Theoretical Background

The unquestionable hegemony of the idea of the positivity of law lasted until the final third of the 19th century on the European continent, throughout the age of the exegetic application of statutory instruments and until the dawn of the free-law movement. Although re-codification was not effected in the second half of the 20th century—with the exception of the direction of development taken by socialist law—and the classical civil codes became gradually reduced from their

classical function of defining the law to the increasingly passive role of being used as mere systemic *locus*-providers and *locus*-indicators of the direction and conceptuality taken by judicial law development,¹ the legal doctrine has nevertheless successfully reduced the disintegration caused by the free-law movement and maintained a positivistic domination for yet another century on the European continent. Though legal positivism was not shattered by the brief rebirth of natural law that took place after the Second World War (as a post-war German reaction to warmongering), finally, the way questions were posed in legal sociology in Europe (from the 1910s on, launched by EUGEN EHRLICH), the American “realist” pragmatism (from the 1930s on, inspired mainly by ROSCOE POUND), the transformation of the new English linguistic and logical analysis of law (from the 1960s on, initiated by H. L. A. HART) into an American-type reconstruction of legal discourses (effective from the 1970s, represented by RONALD DWORKIN), and, at last—as a stroke of grace—in Europe itself, the stabilisation of the so-called anti-formalist stand (formulated by MICHEL VILLEY and CHAÏM PERELMAN) in the debate on law and logic and its progress into a reconstructive inquiry of legal processes, on the one hand, and the foundation of a continental theory of argumentation, cultivated almost as a substitute for legal dogmatics (mainly introduced by ROBERT ALEXY and AULIS AARNIO), on the other—well, all these challenged the validity of unconditional adherence to legal positivism, even if exclusively in theoretical terms, and made it outdated by the 1980s.² In brief, what had seemed, just a few decades ago, to be a demand (guided by wishful thinking) for the “decline” of legal positivism, is now rather anticipated by several visions—instead of as a stigma of decay—as the image of a positive escape forwards, resulting from its transcendence as transformed into something new, in a way, however, accompanied by a reassuring continuity.³

Nevertheless, the theoretical dominance of legal positivism in its era offered two possibilities: accepting the actual definition of the law through positive law in practical legal processes while explaining any kind of eventual difference as only an exceptional deviance, on the one hand, and also taking the formal and official positivation of the law as a theoretically descriptive conceptual criterion

¹ Cf. Csaba Varga *Codification as a Socio-historical Phenomenon* [1979/1991] 2nd {reprint} ed. with an Annex & Postscript (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2011) viii + 431 pp. & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14200/14231/>>, ch. V para. 5, especially at p. 121.

² For an overview, cf. Csaba Varga *Theory of the Judicial Process The Establishment of Facts* [1991/1995] 2nd {reprint} ed. with Postfaces I and II (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2011) viii + 308 pp. & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15500/15540/>>, ch. I.

³ For the decline, see, e.g., Michel Villey ‘Eessor et décadence du volontarisme juridique’ *Archives de Philosophie du Droit* 3: »Le rôle de la volonté dans le Droit« (Paris: Sirey 1958), pp. 87–136. As to continuity, it is characteristic that—only to take just one telling example—the editor of *Transformation de la culture juridique québécoise* dir. Bjarne Melkevik (Québec: Presses de l’Université Laval 1998) 246 pp., Avant-propos, p. 7, had to leave his working hypothesis behind as unfounded. Albeit the sub-topic of the debate in question was heralded as „Est-ce la fin de l’hégémonie positiviste?”, it does not feature any longer in the printed collection of the proceedings, as the workshop has proven just the antithesis, namely that „l’hégémonie positiviste ne touche nullement à sa fin au Québec, pas plus qu’en d’autres lieux”.

of legal phenomena, on the other. While the latter was cut relatively soon as applied to the notion of juridicity itself,⁴ moreover, the former was also cut back conclusively (and was mainly replaced by explanation within the framework of the processes within an overall autopoietic system),⁵ paradoxically all this has hardly affected the range of problems raised by the structuration of and systematisation in legal systems.

2. Foundations of Structuration and Systematisation Challenged

In the field of continental Civil Law, it seemed to be a self-evident fact, not questioned by anybody until the recent decades, that the very structure of legal systems consists partly of their visible *external division* (according to the branches of the law and, inside any of them, according to its formal sources)—that is, their division into individual branches of the law, including the relevant provisions of the Constitution, the respective code(s) and law(s), the eventual decrees and orders designed to ensure their implementation, as well as the judicial guiding principles issued by decisions for the uniformity of jurisprudence, and also the individual judgements—, and partly of the *internal (logical) self-division* of any legal (normative) regulation resulting from the axiomatic ideal of modern legislation,⁶ that is, the fact that regulation is mostly effected by *general* rules and *particular* dispositions in the *general* as well as the *particular* parts of the law-code in question, on the one hand, and by established *principles, main rules* (disposing of the particular area of regulation), *rules* (breaking them further down in concretisation), *exceptions* (allowing concessions from these), as well as *sub-exceptions* (making additional concessions available with regard to their last

⁴ As a programme and a realisation, cf. Csaba Varga ‘Quelques questions méthodologiques de la formation des concepts en sciences juridiques’ [1970] *Archives de Philosophie du Droit* XVIII (Paris: Sirey 1973), pp. 205–241 {& in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15333/#>>, pp. 7–33}, para. 4, in particular at pp. 223 et seq.

⁵ Cf., as a philosophy of language reconstruction, Csaba Varga ‘The Context of the Judicial Application of Norms’ [1988] in *Prescriptive Formality and Normative Rationality in Modern Legal Systems* Festschrift for Robert S. Summers, ed. Werner Krawietz, Neil MacCormick & Georg Henrik von Wright (Berlin: Duncker & Humblot 1994), pp. 495–512 {& in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15333/#>>, pp. 295–314}; as a restatement characteristic of the critical legal studies, William A. Conklin *The Phenomenology of Modern Legal Discourse* The Judicial Production and the Discourse of Suffering (Aldershot, etc.: Ashgate 1998) xii + 258 pp.; and, as an autopoietic process, Csaba Varga ‘On Judicial Ascertainment of Facts’ *Ratio Juris* [Bologna/Oxford] 4 (1991) 1, pp. 61–71 {or ‘Природа судебного установления фактов’ (пер. Е. Г. Самохина) in Чаба Варга *Загадка права и правового мышления* Избранные произведения; Сост. и науч. ред. М. В. Антонов (Санкт-Петербург: Издательский Дом «Алеф-Пресс» 2015), pp. 238–254}.

It is to be noted that essays on the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries in Central Europe already explored such arguments for theoretical explanation. Cf., above all, Karl Georg Wurzel *Das juristische Denken* (Wien: Verlag Moritz Perles 1904) vi + 102 pp. [trans. Ernest Bruncken as ‘Methods of Juridical Thinking’ in *Science of Legal Method* (Boston: The Boston Book Co. 1917), pp. 286–428 {The Modern Legal Philosophy Series IX}].

⁶ See Csaba Varga ‘The Quest for Formalism in Law: Ideals of Systemicity and Axiomatisability between Utopianism and Heuristic Assertion’ *Acta Juridica Hungarica* 50 (2009) 1, pp. 1–30 {& in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15400/15409>>, pp. 87–123} {or ‘Поиски формализма в праве: Идеи системности и аксиоматичности между утопизмом и эвристическим суждением’ in Варга *Загадка права* (2015), pp. 231–237}.

specification), on the other. All this encountered no problems for a long time, because it was made visible exactly in this way; however, because a number of legal theories (including, of course, that of MARXism) were also trying to find (through simplifyingly viewing law as the reflection of something else, external to and outside of it, hence having to conform in features, structure, etc. to what it is a reflection of) a kind of correspondence between law and the spheres of (social) reality regulated by it, that is, a kind of responsiveness not merely instrumental and/or functional, but also epistemologically interpretable;⁷ as well as because these theories took far too seriously the suggestion of all the positive law's staff on the exclusivity of established juristic methods in legal processes. This was the shift in codification from the casuistry to the axiomatic ideal, the transition from the creative precedential induction (the method of comparing, assimilating and distinguishing those precedents, taking the individual cases as a starting point) to the reproductive, mechanical, and deductive rule-application (starting out from the mass of provisions at various degrees of generality of the code, construed as constituents of one logical system, following the axiomatic ideal).⁸

The DWORKINian theoretical challenge has made it clear that there are principles in every system that are, as to their nature, not only different from the rules but, in fact, control the very policy of the applicability of rules and, thereby, also their actual practice.⁹ Well, it is not by mere chance that, based upon this, it was in the United States of America, the flagship of politicised aspirations and expectations, that the practice known as constitutionalisation (subjecting any issue at will to be reduced to—through being inferred directly from—basic rights or constitutional values)¹⁰ had evolved. In parallel with this, as a result of the compromise between the needs of changing life and the technical availabilities

⁷ Cf., e.g., Mihály Samu *A szocialista jogrendszer tagozódásának alapja* [The basis for the structuring of the socialist legal system] (Budapest: Közgazdasági és Jogi Könyvkiadó 1964) 268 pp., and, as its ontological criticism, Csaba Varga *The Place of Law in Lukács' World Concept* [1981/1985] 3rd {reprint} ed. with Postface (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 218 pp. & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14200/14249/>>, ch. 5, para. 3, especially at pp. 123 et seq.

⁸ Cf. Csaba Varga *The Paradigms of Legal Thinking* [1996] enlarged 2nd ed. (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 418 pp. [Philosophiae Iuris] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14600/14657/>>, ch. 2, para. 1. See also Csaba Varga, as the first critical formulation of its primitive idea, with his proposition to transcend it, 'A magatartási szabály és az objektív igazság kérdése' [Rule of behaviour and the question of objective truth, 1964] in *Útkeresés Kísérletek — kéziratban* [The Search for a Path: Early Essays in Manuscript] (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2001) & <http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15346>, pp. 4–18 [Jogfilozófiák] and, as applied to the paradigm of basis and superstructure in MARXism, Csaba Varga 'Autonomy and Instrumentality of Law in a Superstructural Perspective' [1985] *Acta Juridica Hungarica* 40 (1999) 3–4, pp. 213–235 {& in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14800/14861/>>, pp. 151–175}.

⁹ Since the classical *topos* by Ronald M. Dworkin's 'The Model of Rules' *University of Chicago Law Review* 35 (1967) 1, pp. 14–46 & <https://openyls.law.yale.edu/bitstream/handle/20.500.13051/3028/The_Model_of_Rules.pdf?sequence=2>, his entire oeuvre seems to substantiate the underlying idea mostly in a constitutional context.

¹⁰ For a dissent in a similarly politicised mirror, see Robert H. Bork *Slouching towards Gomorrah* Modern Liberalism and American Decline (New York: Regan Books / Harper-Collins 1997) xiv + 382 pp. Also cf. Csaba Varga 'Humanity Elevating Themselves? Dilemmas of Rationalism in our Age' in *Comparative Legal Cultures On Traditions Classified, their Rapprochement & Transfer, and the Anarchy of Hyper-rationalism* (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 253 pp. [Philosophiae Iuris] & <http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15386>, pp. 131–163.

offered by the law's codification, after the Second World War the German style of legal dogmatics had, as its own construction developed from a practice based on general clauses, already definitely nourished a conception of law that defined it as a texture made up of principles and rules.¹¹

However, just as facts never got to court by themselves, labelled and prepared for a syllogistic inference from the complex of facts and norms¹² (but only as the result of a creative—both normative¹³ and constructive¹⁴—act of the judicial forum taking a decision), similarly, neither the principles nor the rules are given in themselves, separated as such from each other in a way classified according to the law's taxonomic systemicity as bearing their own, separate meanings. As is known, all this can only be the result of a creative act. Based upon the doctrinal study of law, which classifies the law's notions by transforming them into constituents of a legal system, it is the judicial forum, exercising its authority while undertaking its exclusive responsibility to decide, that builds different propositions into (or, properly speaking, uses them in its reasoning openly or implicitly as) either principles or rules, respectively. And, in parallel with this, it is their posterior analytical reconstruction that will also label them, interpreting the immense mass of normative regulations and reasonings, used just as raw materials, as either principles or rules.

3. Is there any Structure or System In-built in the Law?

Does the legal system itself have a structure or system, or is any of them taken into (or given to) it from the outside? And if it is taken, who is taking it? I think it would be absurd to give any kind of negative answer: how would it be possible to transplant any structure into something thought to be unstructured and a-systemic by itself? Or, for the sake of a reasonable answer, we have to hypothesise the legal system as being structured and systematised in itself. However, the questions “what is it?” and “what does it consist of?”, “how is it divided and into what?” and “what is the meaning of this all and of any of its structured or systemic

¹¹ Cf., above all, Robert Alexy *Theorie der Grundrechte* (Baden-Baden: Nomos 1985) 548 pp. [Studien und Materialien zur Verfassungsgerichtsbarkeit 28], and, as built into a coherent theory, Béla Pokol *The Concept of Law The Multi-layered Legal System* (Budapest: Rejtjel 2001) 152 pp., particularly ch. VIII, pp. 90–106. For the overall debate, cf. as well Ewa Poplawska ‘Constitutionalization of the Legal Order’ *Polish Contemporary Law* 1998/1–4, pp. 115–134 & <<https://czasopisma.inp.pan.pl/index.php/cceel/article/download/1035/991/1431>>.

¹² “For court purposes, what the court thinks about the facts is all that matters. For actual events [...] happened in the past. They do not walk into the court.” Jerome Frank *Courts on Trial Myth and Reality in American Justice* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 1949) xii + 441 pp. on p. 15.

¹³ See, e.g., most expressedly by Joachim Israel ‘Is a Non-normative Social Science Possible?’ *Acta Sociologica* 15 (1972) 1, pp. 69–87 and ‘Stipulations and Construction in the Social Sciences’ in *The Context of Social Psychology A Critical Assessment*, ed. J. Israel & H. Tajfel (London & New York: Academic Press 1972), pp. 123–211.

¹⁴ See, e.g., most forcefully, Hans Kelsen *Reine Rechtslehre Einleitung in die rechtswissenschaftliche Problematik* (Leipzig & Wien: Franz Deuticke 1934) xiv + 236 pp.

components?”, as well as “what is the significance of its being structured or systematised?”—well, all these already depend upon the sense given (or, more precisely, attributed) to law.

Formerly, in a somewhat similar context, I already presented the figure of three partially intersecting circles. This was intended to prove, as against the normativist message of legal positivism (claiming that by means of norms alone one can bring about a medium with an own existence, capable of effective operation in social practice), that the criteria for the law set when it has been made positive do not necessarily imply more than mere manifestations of an intention that existed at the time of positivization. Therefore, the concern about what the law was intended to be (i.e., to signify and represent) by its drafter(s) when it was promulgated (e.g., in legislation) is not necessarily identical with the one about what and how the law is being formed into—when re-asserted, adapted or having ceased practically to exist—in either its official “application” (e.g., in judicial practice) or its actual community practice respecting the unofficial and spontaneous, popular ways of customary proceeding as if for legal effect.¹⁵

Figure 14.

Well, we can apply again the aforementioned figure (implying the practice of hermeneutical communities, giving and exchanging meanings) as reflected by the

¹⁵ Cf. Csaba Varga ‘Anthropological Jurisprudence? Leopold Pospíšil and the Comparative Study of Legal Cultures’ [1985] in *Law in East and West* ed. Institute of Comparative Law of the Waseda University (Tokyo 1988), pp. 265–285, especially at pp. 271–272 {& in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15333/#>>, pp. 437–457} {or ‘«Право» или «нечто более или менее правовое» (антропологические рассуждение о том, то есть право)’ in Вапра *Загадка права* (2015), pp. 185–194}.

issue of the internal structuring of the legal system itself, by placing the intersecting circles into a circle partly closed. [Figure]

This is because the legislature may influence the decision to be taken by the legal and/or social community as to what is what amongst the possible structuring or systematising components of the legal system and also as to what kind of one-sided or symmetrical connection is being implied by each of these in what type of horizontal or vertical context. However, we also have to bear in mind that, according to the nature of things, any creature of the legislature can exclusively become productive in the hands and through the understanding of its addressees as clients—as operated by its professional official administrator and/or the practice of non-professionals—through their standardising pattern which, as conventionalisingly re-asserted, may become organised as integrated into social tradition. There is one considerable difference from the instance invoked above, relating to the theoretical understanding of facts, notwithstanding. That is, the entirety of the processes and interactions in question is mediated through and within the bounds of a legal doctrine, that is, by the conceptual sets and contexts of its prevailing dogmatics, constantly refined by both practitioners and scholars of the law, i.e., by dogmatics that albeit mostly lacks officially established and formal qualities, yet exerts, by means of professional socialisation, a nearly exclusive impact upon how the law, as explored and solidified in its internal system, is actually understood and practised. And there is no need to say that the more the legal processes (legislation and administration of justice) are practised and controlled by the legal profession, the more the doctrinal representation and mediation of the law prevails.

4. Structuration and Systematisation as a Meta-construct

In consequence, it is not logic itself that labels anything as a structuring element identified either as a principle or as a rule, but just we, who ponder, as the only possibility, always based upon the more or less successful comprehension of such a doctrine, projected through its re-consideration and reconstructive re-interpretation onto our given question, the mode of constructing a sequence of distinguishing, deduction and justification, which seems to be utilisable and conclusive enough to convince those who control the issue we propose, in the procedural hierarchy. In so doing, we start from a nearly optional formulation of normative language and reasoning (or from any expressions or even fragments of these), and within the boundaries of the internal ‘rules of the [legal] game’ (of how to proceed in identification, argumentation and induction/deduction, etc.) as established and re-confirmed by the legal profession in practice.

Of course, in practice all this appears as dynamism, and not as chaos; as openness to new issues, but by no means unforeseeability lacking any perspective.

This assumes creative and constructive co-operation with normative force on behalf of all actors and, at the same time, a community game processualised in formal sequences, as controlled in multiple ways many times; a game in which, although equal chances are granted to everyone in principle and anyone may innovate or deviate from earlier rules, anybody doing so not only has to give motives and justification for this, but also to derive this as inevitably resulting (even if not perceived and not practised by anybody else so far) from the normative order that is continuously claimed to have remained untouched as a whole, and thereby again re-established and re-asserted (that is, re-conventionalised) in its overall arrangement.¹⁶

As a final conclusion, notwithstanding, in the long run and in their practical continuity, both the structuration and systematisation of the legal system and the considerable stability of the way it is made up can be taken as granted. As opposed to the obvious architectural analogy in this case, our edifice is not built into one single construction by assembling components originating from different sources and made up of different elements—in architecture, bricks, mortar and plaster. On the contrary, we build and live the lawyer’s profession using the only material at our disposal, language, in which words are selected to refer to concepts so that a suitable series of intellectual (logical) operations can be performed.¹⁷ Well, the question of which word stands in the place of what (the role it will be used in and what it will refer to in the given hermeneutical situation) depends, in addition to the language use socialised and conventionalised,¹⁸ in a direct sense exclusively on those who perform the intellectual (logical) operation in question. And the person concerned is involved as a hermeneutical actor in the given circles of communication, on the one hand, and, at the same time, is also an actor in some sociological situation, on the other, who, in average cases, will act in the way he is expected to, not exceeding the justifiable boundaries of his/her professional socialisation(s).

¹⁶ All this recalls the obvious parallel with the challenge of EUCLID’s geometry by BOLYAI and LOBACHEVSKY. “From an external point of view [...] the creation of »another new world« is manifest in the choice between equally eligible incidentalities and the presentation of the selected variant as perfect and logically necessary. [...] This concerns conceptualisation, namely the fact that conceptual systems, be they as perfect as possible from an internal point of view or had they the most convincing explanatory force when describing the external world, can merely be regarded as mental experiments. They are nothing but games, which we make use of *faute de mieux*.” Csaba Varga *Lectures on the Paradigms of Legal Thinking* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó 1999) vii + 279 pp. [Philosophiae Iuris], p. 38.

It is to be noted, however, that legal systems that have achieved a mature and balanced state are characterised exactly by the conscious institutionalisation of the ability to challenge the system from within the system (as their own judicial solution on account of gaps in the law unfillable otherwise, pursuant to, e.g., overruling precedents in England or § 1 (2) of the Swiss *Zivilgesetzbuch*); however, due to the self-disciplining force of the system, this does not proliferate in practice, being resorted to as a corrective measure only as a last resort.

¹⁷ For the stand of logic and conceptuality in human thinking, cf. Csaba Varga ‘Az ellentmondás természete’ [The nature of contradiction, 1989] in his *Útkeresés* (2001), pp. 138–139.

¹⁸ Cf., e.g., François Ost ‘Le code et le dictionnaire: Acceptabilité linguistique et validité juridique’ *Sociologie et sociétés* XVIII (avril 1986) 1, pp. 59–75.

It can be established, therefore, that in our human world one acts amongst and as confronted with a huge number of various *donnés*—that is, given components—crystallised in conventionalised (and continuously re-conventionalising) tradition, that is, *donnés* that never stand by themselves as they are never freed from their human-given meaning. Time after time *construits*—that is, composite structures that have been constructed—are being generated out of these, for and to the benefit of a man performing an action, which will be transmitted to his fellows and to the posterity, only to become a tradition that, in its turn, will be further handed down again merely in its quality as a *donné*.¹⁹ Well, if we inquire, in an ontological sense, about the continuity and practicality of these and the safety of their meaningful transmission, we can confirm that, throughout the historical process of conventionalisations, a kind of “tendential unity”²⁰ can always be safely recognised—both in the sense of the actuality of their functional correspondence to the overall social practice and of the reliability of their materialisation through speech acts.

All in all, my contribution to the conference on »Systematization in Law: The ‘Magic Glass’ of the Codifier« in tribute for the 250th anniversary of the birth of МИХАИЛ МИХАЙЛОВИЧ СПЕРАНСКИЙ has intended to present, as a basis, the elementary component of the idea underlying the questions set forth above, namely, the apparent paradox traceable in it, according to which structuring and systematising in law are, in their massive incidence, construed/constructed and construing/constructing at the same time, for they do not and cannot exist in and by themselves at all.

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¹⁹ Expression of FRANÇOIS GÉNY; cf. <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/François_Gény>.

²⁰ Expression of GEORGE LUKÁCS; cf. Varga *The Place of Law...* (2012).

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